

GEDI reveals decline in overstorey and increase in understorey canopy cover of protected forests in Central Europe since 2019

Xiao Liu^{a,*}, Vítězslav Moudrý^b, Bernhard Schuldt^c, Matthias Forkel^a

^a TUD Dresden University of Technology, Institute of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, Dresden 01062, Germany

^b Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Department of Spatial Sciences, Kamýčká 129, Praha-Suchbát 165 00, Czech Republic

^c TUD Dresden University of Technology, Institute of Forest Botany and Forest Zoology, Tharandt 01737, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Drought and insect disturbances have resulted in widespread forest dieback in the forests of Central Europe since 2018. However, the implications of these changes in forest cover on the vertical structure, such as the canopy cover of the overstorey and understorey, have yet to be investigated at a large scale. By making use of the Global Ecosystem Dynamic Investigation (GEDI) spaceborne waveform lidar, we show here that overstorey canopy cover has declined and understorey canopy cover has increased in both coniferous and broadleaved protected forests in Central Europe since 2019. The observed loss of overstorey canopy cover is consistent with results from other remote sensing-based forest monitoring products. However, only GEDI has the capability to detect the increase in understorey canopy cover. For example, in Harz Mountains in Germany, overstorey canopy cover decreases by approximately 4.45 % per year in coniferous forests and by approximately 1.57 % per year in broadleaved forests, while understorey canopy cover increases by approximately 1.18 % and 0.59 %, respectively. For coniferous forests, we find that changes in overstorey canopy cover have a significant negative correlation ($r = -0.78$, $p < 0.01$) with changes in understorey canopy cover. However, this relationship is not significant for broadleaved forests. This implies that canopy mortality in coniferous forests is more likely to trigger succession in the understorey than in broadleaved forests. This study demonstrates a new perspective for monitoring the dynamics of forest overstorey and understorey using spaceborne lidar, which can help improve understanding of feedbacks between forests and climate.

1. Introduction

Forests across Europe are increasingly affected by disturbances, but the dominant drivers vary considerably by region. In Southern Europe, wildfires are a major cause of tree mortality, whereas in Central Europe—the focus of this study—storms and insect outbreaks prevail (Senf et al., 2020; Senf and Seidl, 2021a). Despite overall forest expansion in parts of Europe (Ceccherini et al., 2020), canopy mortality in temperate forests has doubled between 1984 and 2016 (Senf et al., 2018). Since 2018, a series of severe drought events has altered forest growth trajectories and triggered extensive dieback (Buras et al., 2021; Michel et al., 2023; Schuldt et al., 2020; Thom et al., 2023). Disturbance activity has remained high in Central Europe even after the extreme drought year (Senf and Seidl, 2021b), driven by both biotic factors such as bark beetle outbreaks and pathogens, and abiotic factors including drought, heat, and wind (Potocic et al., 2021). In some cases, these

disturbances were locally followed by wildfires (Beetz et al., 2025). Tree mortality and disturbances cause a decline of the carbon sink potential in European forests (Migliavacca et al., 2025). While many temperate forests show resilience to individual events such as storms and beetle outbreaks (Cerioni et al., 2024; Senf and Seidl, 2022), long-term monitoring indicates a general increase in crown defoliation across both coniferous and broadleaved species between 2013 and 2022 (Michel et al., 2023). These developments highlight the need to better understand how different forest strata respond to disturbance, particularly the dynamics between overstorey and understorey layers.

Forests are vertically structured into overstorey and understorey layers. The overstorey, composed of tall and mature trees, forms the continuous upper canopy that drives photosynthesis, sequesters carbon, and regulates microclimatic conditions such as light, temperature, and humidity (Bechtold, 2003; De Frenne, 2024; Oliver and Larson, 1996; Stiers et al., 2019). The understorey comprises the vegetation beneath

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: xiao.liu@mailbox.tu-dresden.de (X. Liu).

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this canopy, including shrubs, young trees and saplings that play a key role in regeneration. It typically responds more quickly to disturbances, thereby contributing to ecosystem resilience and maintaining essential ecosystem functions (Matuszkiewicz et al., 2024). Despite the ecological importance of these vertical strata, their dynamics and interactions under disturbance regimes remain poorly understood at large spatial and temporal scales.

To assess how disturbances and recovery processes differentially affect overstorey and understorey, monitoring tools that resolve vertical canopy structure across broad spatial and temporal scales are needed. Tree canopy cover, defined as the proportion of ground area occupied by the vertical projection of tree crowns, is a widely used indicator of forest structure and dynamics (Tang et al., 2019). Changes in canopy cover provide valuable information on disturbance impacts (Hansen et al., 2013; Senf et al., 2018) as well as recovery processes (Mandl et al., 2024; Senf and Seidl, 2022). However, most existing canopy cover products are derived from passive optical remote sensing (Hadi et al., 2016; Hansen et al., 2013, 2002; Korhonen et al., 2017; Potapov et al., 2024; Thonfeld et al., 2022). While effective for monitoring broad trends, passive optical sensors cannot reliably disentangle signals from overstorey and understorey layers (Liu et al., 2017; Pisek et al., 2015a, 2015b). Radar-based approaches, such as tomographic synthetic aperture radar, can retrieve vertical forest structure using long-wavelength microwave bands (e.g., L- and P-band) (Pardini et al., 2018). Yet, the complex scattering mechanisms of radar signals make it difficult to relate reflectivity to biophysical properties at specific canopy layers. Consequently, most disturbance and recovery assessments do not separate overstorey and understorey dynamics and hence potentially underestimate mortality in the overstorey and overlooking understorey regrowth as a pathway of recovery.

In contrast, light detection and ranging (lidar) directly captures vertical forest structure by recording the return time of laser pulses

penetrating canopy gaps. Multi-temporal lidar observations from ground-based (Calders et al., 2023, 2015; Li et al., 2018; Nunes et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2019) and airborne platforms (Korpela et al., 2023; Meng et al., 2018; Tompalski et al., 2021) have demonstrated strong potential for quantifying structural changes. Yet, such campaigns are often restricted to limited areas and lack long-term temporal coverage (Guerra-Hernández et al., 2024a). NASA's Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) is the first spaceborne lidar designed to map vertical forest structure at near-global scale (Dubayah et al., 2020a). Despite its sampling design, GEDI has already yielded promising insights into structural disturbance and recovery (East et al., 2023; Guerra-Hernández et al., 2024b; Holcomb et al., 2024; Huettermann et al., 2023; Kacic et al., 2023; Lin et al., 2024; Turubanova et al., 2023; Ziegler et al., 2023). However, its potential for monitoring canopy cover dynamics across overstorey and understorey strata at large spatial scales and fine temporal resolution (e.g., monthly) remains underexplored.

The first phase of the GEDI mission, conducted from 2019 to 2023, produced the most accurate near-global canopy cover product currently available. The GEDI Level 2B product (Dubayah et al., 2021b) provides cumulative canopy cover profiles at the footprint level with a vertical step size of 5 m, enabling measurement of both overstorey and understorey cover (Fig. 1). Although the accuracy of lidar in measuring understorey cover can be limited due to signal attenuation by the overstorey (Hamraz et al., 2017; Mandl et al., 2023), the ability of GEDI to detect understorey canopy cover largely depends on forest structure (Fig. 1). Applying a reasonable height threshold can help mitigate this limitation (Tang and Dubayah, 2017). Using a fixed threshold (e.g., 10 m) to distinguish between overstorey and understorey, GEDI detects understorey canopy cover in undisturbed forests primarily from small trees growing in open spaces between taller trees (Fig. 1a and d). As overstorey canopy cover declines, lidar signals are increasingly able to penetrate canopy gaps and reach vegetation in the understorey (Fig. 1b

Fig. 1. Concept of overstorey and understorey canopy cover as seen by GEDI 25 m footprints in three cases with example photos from different forests, adapted from (Du et al., 2021) and (Tang and Armston, 2020). The red dashed line defines a fixed boundary of 10 m between overstorey and understorey. The shaded area represents the lidar reflectance. The filled area at top represents GEDI canopy cover. The ellipses within the canopies represent the gaps in the canopy, where lidar signals can reach ground. The red cross represents understorey that is not detected by lidar.

and e). Following overstorey defoliation, shrubs and small trees begin to grow, and GEDI is capable of capturing this regeneration process (Fig. 1c and f), offering valuable insights into forest succession.

In this study, we aim to investigate changes in the vertical forest structure in Central Europe that have occurred since the drought year of 2018, using GEDI observations from forests characterized by similar management strategies and complex structural compositions. Our objectives are to: (1) quantify the rate of forest overstorey canopy loss, (2) quantify the rate of understorey regrowth, and (3) analyse the relationship between forest overstorey loss and understorey regrowth to demonstrate forest recovery across European forests. Our results were validated using other forest loss products. Given that the next phase of the GEDI mission has been launched and the sensor has been active again since April 2024, we aim to provide a methodological approach for integrating data from both mission phases to assess forest dynamics over the long term.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Study region and study sites

Our study region is Central Europe, covering seven countries, i.e., Austria, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, and Switzerland. Within each country, we used protected areas larger than 25 km² as study sites based on the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA, January 2024 version, UNEP-WCMC and IUCN, 2024). We used the categories of protected areas defined by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), which in our study region include 690 protected landscapes: 5 category Ib, 27 category II, 46 category IV, 609 category V and 3 category VI (Table S1). Protected areas were selected as study sites for two reasons: (1) they enable the aggregation of GEDI footprints from forests with similar management practices, and (2) the vertical structure in protected areas is generally more complex than in unprotected areas (Ceccherini et al., 2023), making them more likely to exhibit multi-layered canopies. The topography and locations of the selected protected areas are shown in Fig. 2. GEDI is mounted on the International Space Station (ISS), which follows an inclined orbit with a 51.6° inclination angle. As a result, GEDI achieves a higher density of observations near 51.6° latitude, where ISS ground tracks converge, leading to increased sampling in this region (Fig. 2b). In contrast, there are fewer GEDI measurements between 51.6° N and 52.5° N, a gap caused by the rotation of the GEDI sensor (up to 5.6°) on its ISS mount (Dubayah et al., 2020b). Due to this spatial sampling pattern, protected areas located above 52.5° N latitude were excluded from the analysis.

2.2. Analysis of changes in GEDI canopy cover

We acquired GEDI data for the period April 2019 to March 2023. GEDI version 2 Level 2B product (Dubayah et al., 2021b) was used here. The GEDI canopy cover is calculated by (Tang and Armston, 2020):

$$CC(z) = (1 - P_{gap}(z, \theta)) \times \cos\theta \quad (1)$$

$$P_{gap}(z, \theta) = 1 - \frac{R_v(z)}{R_v(0) + R_g \times \frac{\rho_v}{\rho_g}} \quad (2)$$

Whereby $CC(z)$ is the cumulative canopy cover from the top of the canopy to a certain height z above ground. Hence, $CC(0)$ is the total canopy cover and $P_{gap}(z, \theta)$ is the directional gap probability at height z with viewing angle θ , which is usually less than 6°. $P_{gap}(z, \theta)$ is estimated using the integrated laser energy $R_v(z)$, ground returned energy R_g , and the canopy to ground reflectance ratio ρ_v/ρ_g , which has a pre-launch global average value of 1.5 and is planned to be updated after launch. The ρ_v/ρ_g value from the available GEDI Level 2B product for this study is still 1.5. GEDI footprints were filtered according to GEDI L2A quality flag, L2B quality flag, total canopy cover, sensitivity, RH100 and terrain slope (Table S2).

We partitioned overstorey (>10 m) and understorey (≤10 m) canopy cover for each GEDI footprint to remain robust to the 5 m vertical binning of GEDI L2B and to avoid cutpoints near the canopy cover uncertainty (~10%). Overstorey canopy cover is hence the cumulative canopy cover from 10 m above ground to the top of the canopy. Understorey canopy cover is the cumulative canopy cover from ground to 10 m (i.e., the difference between total canopy cover and overstorey canopy cover). Although the minimum height of forests is defined as 5 m by FAO (2020), we chose 10 m rather than 5 m because of the trade-off between accuracy and vertical resolution (Tang et al., 2016). Sensitivity tests with a 5 m and a height-adaptive threshold yielded consistent patterns (Section 4.3).

Because GEDI does not have regular revisits over the same location, a spatiotemporal aggregation is necessary for generating the time series at specific areas. The IUCN protected areas were used to mask all filtered GEDI footprints. In order to stratify our analysis with forest type, we use the Copernicus 10-metre resolution forest type product for the year 2018 (European Environment Agency, 2020). This dataset is derived from the Sentinel-2 satellite and contains three categories: non-forest areas, coniferous forests and broadleaved forests. It has an overall accuracy of around 96%, validated through the interpretation of high resolution satellite images. We resampled this dataset to 25 m spatial resolution using mode resampling. GEDI footprints were grouped by forest type within each protected area. Monthly time series of canopy cover in overstorey and understorey were generated by taking the median value

Fig. 2. Overview of the study region in Central Europe. (a) GEDI DEM at 1 km spatial resolution (Dubayah et al., 2021a). (b) Density of high quality GEDI footprints (number of footprints per km²) in IUCN protected areas. The blue dashed line shows 52.5° N and the grey dash line shows 51.6° N, which corresponds to the ISS inclination angle 51.6°. The red triangle shows the location of an example site in east Harz Mountains, Germany (Section S2 and S3).

of footprints collected in the same month. Only months with more than 20 footprints were used. For protected areas with two forest types, time series for both forest types were calculated.

To quantify changes in overstorey and understorey canopy cover from 2019 to 2023, we first applied the Seasonal and Trend decomposition using Loess (STL) method (Cleveland et al., 1990) to remove seasonality from monthly GEDI time series, and secondly applied the Theil-Sen estimator (Sen, 1968; Theil, 1992) to the seasonality removed time series. Missing values in the monthly time series were substituted using linear interpolation. We used a window size of 13 to extract the seasonal component because there is usually one phenological circle of 12 months per year in Central European forests. To mitigate the influence of irregular GEDI acquisition dates on the following time series decomposition and Theil-slope estimation, only areas with: (1) at least 24 months with observations, and (2) at least 3 months repeating 4 times between April 2019 and March 2024 were used.

After removing the seasonal component in canopy cover time series, Theil-Sen slope was estimated from the remaining part to describe the change of canopy cover over time. The Theil-Sen estimator is a nonparametric linear regression method that is insensitive to outliers. For each time series, we calculated the Theil-Sen slope, intercept, and 90 % confidence interval (CI) width of Theil-Sen slope as a measure of uncertainty. In this study, the intercept was calculated by $y_{median} - slope * x_{median}$. We then transformed the unit of estimated Theil-Sen slope from percentage per month to percentage per year by multiplying with 12 in order to have a unit comparable to other studies that report changes per year. An example of the proposed workflow is presented in Section S2. We used Python library statsmodels (version 0.14.0) (Seabold and Perktold, 2010) to implement STL. Theil-Sen slope was calculated using Python library SciPy (version 1.11.2) (Virtanen et al., 2020).

2.3. Comparison with ancillary datasets

2.3.1. Hansen Global Forest Change 2000-2023

In order to compare changes in over- and understorey canopy cover with forest loss, we used the Global Forest Change dataset from 2000 to 2023 (Hansen et al., 2013) (version 1.11, referred as ‘‘Hansen dataset’’). It provides annual updates of gross forest cover loss (*lossyear*), which represents the year when there is a change from forest (> 50 % tree cover) to non-forest (around 0 % tree cover) per pixel, i.e., stand-replacement disturbance. This dataset does not distinguish forest loss because of management, harvest or natural disturbances. It was created by using a decision tree to estimate annual tree cover from Landsat images collected during growing seasons. This dataset has values between 00 and 23, with 00 indicating no forest loss and value > 00 indicating forest loss in the year 2001–2023. The derived forest loss has an overall accuracy of 99.8 % in temperate forests. However, there is no validation of forest loss after 2012 yet. Hansen dataset is provided with one arc-second spatial resolution (around 30 m at the equator). This resolution is comparable to GEDI 25 m footprint so we did not resample Hansen data to match with GEDI footprints.

To compare Hansen forest loss with GEDI canopy cover change, we firstly calculated the percentage of forest loss for each forest type by:

$$PC_{forest\ loss} = \frac{N_{forest\ loss}}{N_{forest\ type2018}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

$N_{forest\ loss}$ is the number of pixels with *lossyear* values between 19 and 22, which was counted using both *lossyear* data and forest type data. $N_{forest\ type2018}$ is the number of pixels covering same forest type in 2018, which was counted using the forest type data regardless of the forest loss in 2018. Similarly as for GEDI canopy cover change, there are two $PC_{forest\ loss}$ values for areas covering both forest types.

2.3.2. Forest Structure Germany

The Forest Structure dataset from Kacic et al. (2023) (referred as ‘‘Kacic dataset’’) provides an annual mapping of forest structure at 10 m spatial resolution for Germany from 2017 to 2022. In this dataset, forest total canopy cover, canopy height and above-ground biomass density were estimated using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 through a Random Forest regression model, with GEDI attributes as response variables. GEDI data collected from June to August is used for model development, whereby the data was split into a training (70 %) and testing (30 %) set. The root mean square error of modelled total canopy cover against testing samples is 18.4 % in 2019 and 19.7 % in 2022 for all forest types. We used total canopy cover data in 2019 and 2022 to compare with our results.

Kacic’s total canopy cover dataset was firstly aggregated to 25 m spatial resolution using bilinear resampling. The difference of total canopy cover (TCC) from 2019 to 2022 was then calculated by:

$$\Delta_{TCC} = TCC_{2022} - TCC_{2019} \quad (4)$$

where TCC_{2019} and TCC_{2022} is total canopy cover in 2019 and 2022, respectively. A positive Δ_{TCC} means an increase and a negative Δ_{TCC} means a decrease in total canopy cover from 2019 to 2022. For each protected area, using forest type data as a mask, the median value of Δ_{TCC} was used to represent the change of total canopy cover for each forest type. We compared Δ_{TCC} (%) rather than $\Delta_{TCC}/4$ (% per year) with GEDI canopy cover change (% per year) because Δ_{TCC} represents the change of average total canopy cover from June to August.

3. Results

3.1. Canopy cover changes in Central Europe

Across protected areas in Central Europe, both coniferous and broadleaved forests show a decline in overstorey canopy cover (Fig. 3). In contrast to the overstorey canopy cover, most areas show positive change of understorey canopy cover for both forest types. The change of overstorey canopy cover in all broadleaved forests is mostly between – 10 and + 5 % per year, while it can be greater than – 10 % per year in coniferous forests (Fig. 4). The increase in understorey canopy cover is slower than the decrease in overstorey canopy cover. For coniferous forests, there is a significant negative linear correlation (Pearson $r = -0.78$) between the canopy cover change in overstorey and understorey (Fig. 4a). A linear regression model shows that, for example, a 10 % reduction in overstorey canopy cover per year change corresponds to an increase of about 2.7 % understorey canopy cover per year. However, in broadleaved forests there is no significant linear correlation between canopy cover change in overstorey and that in understorey (Fig. 4b). The filtering of protected areas seems to have little effect on this relationship (grey points in Fig. 4). The 90 % confidence interval of GEDI canopy cover changes ranges at most sites between 0 to up to 4.5 % per year (Figure S11). GEDI canopy cover change in overstorey of broadleaved forests shows the largest confidence interval.

Coniferous forests with a faster decline in overstorey canopy cover demonstrate greater forest loss and total canopy cover change (Figure S14 a and c). The detected GEDI canopy cover change in overstorey of coniferous forest is consistent with the Hansen forest loss dataset ($r = -0.89$, $p < 0.01$) and Kacic dataset ($r = 0.81$, $p < 0.01$) (Figure S15 a and e). The larger the forest loss or total canopy cover change in coniferous forests is, the faster the understorey grows (Figure S15 b and f). In contrast, in broadleaved forests, the relationship between GEDI canopy cover change and percentage of forest loss is much weaker (Figure S15 c and d). There is no significant relationship between our results and Kacic dataset in broadleaved forests (Figure S15 g and h). It indicates that using total canopy cover fails to capture the canopy mortality in broadleaved forests, and the observed increase in total canopy cover mostly comes from growth of understorey.

Fig. 3. GEDI canopy cover change from April 2019 and March 2023 in (a) overstorey and (b) understorey in coniferous forests, and (c) overstorey and (d) understorey in broadleaved forests. The grey areas present areas filtered according to Section 2.2. The results for all protected areas are presented in Figure S10.

Fig. 4. Correlation analysis between GEDI canopy cover change in overstorey and understorey for: (a) coniferous and (b) broadleaved forests. N is the number of protected areas after filtering. The grey points represent areas without filtering. Each point in the scatter plots represents one protected area. r is the Pearson coefficient between canopy cover change of overstorey and understorey after filtering. For coniferous forests, a linear regression model was fitted using change of overstorey (x) and understorey canopy cover (y).

For each forest type, we ranked the protected areas according to the GEDI overstorey canopy cover change. The 15 areas with strongest overstorey cover decline and their corresponding understorey canopy

cover change are presented in Fig. 5. GEDI canopy cover change for all protected areas are available at the online dataset accompanying this study (Liu et al., 2025). The uncertainty of canopy cover change in

Fig. 5. Protected areas ranked by 15 strongest declines in overstorey canopy cover in (a) coniferous forests and (b) broadleaved forests. The whisker shows 90 % confidence interval of GEDI canopy cover change. The red shaded bar shows the percentage of forest loss (%) in each protected area according to the Hansen dataset. The dashed line indicates no canopy cover change.

understorey is smaller than overstorey for both forest types. However, the uncertainty in overstorey canopy cover change is generally larger in broadleaved forests than in coniferous forests. This likely reflects stronger seasonal variability in broadleaved canopies, which increases uncertainty in estimating the Theil–Sen slope of the deseasonalized series when GEDI observations are sparse. Notably, we found that this ranking according to the GEDI overstorey canopy cover change does not fully match with percentage of forest loss derived using Hansen Global Forest Change 2000–2023 data. In coniferous forests, these areas with strong decline in overstorey canopy cover have lost between 40 % and 70 % forest from 2019 to 2022. Meanwhile, in broadleaved forests, these areas with strong decline in overstorey canopy cover have lost less typically less than 5 %, only 5 out of 15 lost more than 10 %.

3.2. Canopy cover changes per country

The change of canopy cover in overstorey and understorey was also analysed per country (Fig. 6). For each country, all GEDI footprints within protected areas larger than 25 km² were used to estimate GEDI canopy cover change with method mentioned in Section 2.2. For coniferous and broadleaved forests, there is a decline in overstorey canopy cover and an increase in understorey canopy cover for all countries. Germany has the fastest decline in overstorey canopy cover while Czechia has the fastest increase in understorey canopy cover.

4. Discussion

4.1. Ecological interpretation of changes in canopy cover

Our results suggest that state-of-the-art forest loss datasets provide

an overly simplified representation of forest loss and canopy cover change in Central Europe. For example, a detected forest loss is often, particularly in coniferous forests, associated with a decline in overstorey canopy cover and a simultaneous increase in understorey canopy cover. In such cases, the change does not indicate an actual loss of forest but rather reflects natural or human-induced forest dynamics. Conversely, forest loss products may easily under detect substantial changes in canopy structure. For instance, if forest loss is defined as a decline in total canopy cover exceeding 50 %, a decline of 40 % would not be classified as forest loss. However, if this 40 % decline in total canopy cover results from a significant reduction in overstorey canopy cover (e. g., –60 %) combined with an increase in understorey canopy cover (e. g., +20 %), it can still have substantial impacts on forest ecosystem dynamics. Therefore, it is crucial to incorporate the vertical dimension of forests into mapping efforts in order to more accurately capture the true dynamics of forest loss.

The increase in understorey canopy cover could be caused by the exposure of already existing plants on the forest floor to GEDI laser beams after the overstorey canopy is defoliated or removed. However, increased lidar penetration is not the sole driver of the detected rise in understorey canopy cover for several reasons. Firstly, while dense closed-canopy forests provide shade, vegetation cover on forest floors is generally very low in due to limited light availability (Fig. 7a and b) (Leuschner and Ellenberg, 2017). This suggests that, even in the absence of occlusion by the overstorey, the existing understorey vegetation alone is unlikely to contribute substantially to the observed increase in GEDI understorey canopy cover. Secondly, there is a significant correlation between the decline in overstorey and the increase in understorey only in coniferous forests, whereas no such correlation is observed in broadleaved forests (Fig. 4). In coniferous forests, the understorey is

Fig. 6. The time series of overstorey and understorey canopy cover for the analysed protected areas per country. For each forest type (Bro – Broadleaved, Con – Coniferous), the median value and 90 % confidence interval of GEDI canopy cover change are shown in the text. The shaded interval shows the 0.25 and 0.75 quantile of canopy cover at each month.

typically less developed because of the dense and year-round shading by the overstorey canopy (Fig. 7c) (Díaz-Calafat et al., 2023). Tree mortality in these forests can markedly increase light availability, thereby triggering rapid growth of understorey vegetation (Matuszkiewicz et al., 2024). This effect is more pronounced in coniferous forests due to the greater contrast in light conditions before and after canopy mortality. In contrast, many broadleaved forests have a well-developed understorey or experience seasonal understorey growth due to increased light availability, especially in spring (Fig. 7d). Consequently, the natural baseline level of understorey vegetation is higher in many broadleaved forests, making any increase after canopy mortality less pronounced (Barbier et al., 2008). Thirdly, a seasonal increase in overstorey canopy

cover, such as during spring, does not lead to a corresponding decrease in understorey canopy cover in GEDI observations (Figure S2). This seasonal behaviour in overstorey and understorey dynamics suggests that understorey vegetation is already detectable by GEDI lidar before overstorey canopy loss occurs. Therefore, the observed increase in understorey canopy cover from 2019 to 2023 is not solely due to the exposure of pre-existing vegetation to the laser beams, but also reflects active succession processes involving the growth of herbs, shrubs, and young trees (Fig. 7e and f).

Long-term in-situ measurements of forest conditions are required to further interpret variations of GEDI canopy cover over time. For example, the StrucNet (Calders et al., 2023) project will provide

Fig. 7. Examples of the understorey in forests in the study region. (a) Coniferous forest without understorey vegetation. (b) Broadleaved forest without understorey. (c) Coniferous forest with herbaceous and dwarf shrub understorey vegetation. (d) Broadleaved forest with natural regrowth in the understorey. (e) Coniferous forest with forest loss in 2020 and standing dead wood. (f) Coniferous forest with forest loss in 2021 and large open gaps with regeneration.

promising validation dataset, especially for validating the magnitude of estimated growth speed of understorey canopy cover in this study. However, there is no such dataset available in Central Europe yet. Therefore, GEDI canopy cover (collected between May and October) and Hansen forest loss data were used additionally to investigate forest regeneration since 2000 in an example region in Harz, Germany (Section S3). The results show, regardless of using 5 m or 10 m as the boundary between overstorey and understorey, understorey canopy cover in both forest types grows after 20 years since forest loss. However, with 5 m as boundary, understorey canopy cover shows increase first and then becomes stable around 10 % after 8 years for coniferous and 14 years for broadleaved forests. This pattern is different from results using 10 m as boundary, where understorey canopy cover shows a linear increase with constant growth rate. It may be because that plants below 5 m such as shrubs stop growing while tree canopies above 5 m continue growing. With the further development of tree canopies, there will be less understorey plants because of increasing competition for light. In conclusion, by combining GEDI canopy cover and Hansen forest loss data, this analysis demonstrates that there is indeed increase in understorey canopy cover after forest loss, i.e., decline in total canopy cover $\geq 50\%$. This increase continues for several years after forest loss. Therefore, forest regeneration should be the main driver for the increase in understorey canopy cover.

The natural regeneration is also affected by the gap size (Hammond and Pokorný, 2020). In Central Europe, the canopy cover could recover to pre-disturbance level within approximately 30 years and the recovery becomes slower for large disturbance patches (> 10 ha) (Senf and Seidl, 2022). However, we found no clear relationship between the area of disturbed forests and GEDI canopy cover change between 2019 and 2022 (Figure S16).

4.2. Suitability of GEDI to detect changes in canopy cover

The spatial sampling of GEDI complicates analyses of multi-year changes as the same location is barely observed twice (Holcomb et al., 2024). Hence, time series need to be spatially aggregated to obtain a sufficient number of observations over time and this aggregation together with seasonal variations in canopy cover can introduce biases on estimating the canopy cover change. To test the effect of the number of observations on the estimated changes in canopy cover, we repeated the analysis by using all GEDI observations, i.e. by not applying the quality filters. The magnitude of canopy cover change does not change with the number of monthly observations, however, forests with few GEDI observations can show unrealistic extreme changes in canopy cover, which is likely caused by an infrequent and temporally uneven

distribution of observations (Figure S12 a-b for coniferous forests and Figure S13 a-b for broadleaved forests). The confidence interval width of GEDI canopy cover change increases initially and then decreases when the number of monthly observations grows (Figure S12 c-d, Figure S13 c-d). For both forest types, the median of CI width reaches to the highest peak when there are about 35 monthly observations. When there are more monthly observations, the seasonal components in the canopy cover time series are more likely to be removed and the remaining components follow a linear relationship, resulting in a decrease in CI width. To increase the number of GEDI monthly observations, the only solution at this time is to increase the spatial extent for aggregation. For example, many smaller protected areas in western Germany (e.g., 50.47°N-51.74°N, 7.07°E-8.82°E) were filtered out because of limited GEDI observations over time. However, their pattern is consistent with Hansen's forest loss data and Kacic's total canopy cover difference data. These smaller protected areas can be merged with neighbouring protected areas to form dense time series for estimating reliable GEDI canopy cover change. The recommissioning of GEDI in 2024 could extend this study to a longer period. The increase of multi-temporal observations will improve the stability of our method. Besides this landscape-scale analysis, forest structure change after disturbance could also be implemented at footprint scale by exploring spatially near-coincident GEDI footprints (Holcomb et al., 2024). In this case, the results will be more sensitive to GEDI geolocation accuracy.

If there are sufficient monthly GEDI observations for removing the seasonality in canopy cover time series, the seasonal variation in the canopy to ground reflectance ratio ρ_v/ρ_g may still introduce biases. For each GEDI footprint, ρ_v/ρ_g is a key parameter for estimating the canopy cover profile (Armston et al., 2013; Li et al., 2024; Ni-Meister et al., 2001; Tang and Armston, 2020). This ratio depends on forest type and varies over space and time, but is set to a constant value (1.5) in the current GEDI Level 2B product. An overestimation of ρ_v/ρ_g can lead to an underestimation of the canopy cover at different height layers and vice versa, as shown in Eq. (2). With a 1 km² spatial window (extended to 3 km² when there is insufficient data for regression) and a 3 months temporal window, Li et al. (2024) updated ρ_v/ρ_g using a linear regression method. They found that the updated ratio (mainly between 1 and 1.5) can improve the estimation of the canopy cover profile in broadleaf, needleleaf and mixed forests. The improvement occurs mainly for forests with moderate canopy cover (between 20 % and 80 %). This regression method assumes that ρ_v/ρ_g is constant for the adjacent footprints within a local area. It requires a large number of samples with different vegetation and ground backscatter components (Armston et al., 2013). We did not update this ratio because (1) this study only considered protected forests, and (2) the GEDI footprints were aggregated monthly per

forest type. Therefore, there is usually insufficient data for implementing the regression method. Repeated airborne laser scanning measurements are required in future work to investigate the seasonal change in ρ_v/ρ_g and its influence on the estimation of canopy cover profile.

In addition, the Copernicus Forest Type 2018 data was used to aggregate GEDI footprints with the same forest type. This dataset represents the forest type before the changes under investigation. It does not consider the post-disturbance regeneration, which could develop to a different forest type than the pre-disturbance forest. This might be especially the case in many sites with a decline in overstorey canopy cover that are classified as coniferous forest in 2018, where the increase of understorey cover might be driven by deciduous early-successional shrub and tree species.

4.3. Effects of the method to separate understorey and overstorey vegetation

To our knowledge, few studies have evaluated methods for using GEDI to map overstorey and understorey canopy cover (Li et al., 2024; Mandl et al., 2023; Yun et al., 2023). In this study, we applied a fixed 10 m threshold to separate overstorey from understorey vegetation. A limitation of this boundary is the inability to distinguish between small trees (<10 m) and the lower canopy elements of tall trees (>10 m). To address this, we tested alternative approaches.

First, we repeated the analysis using a 5 m threshold. However, GEDI canopy cover below 5 m is typically < 10 %, approaching GEDI's measurement error (Section S2 and S7). Still, the main conclusions are consistent with those from the 10 m threshold: (1) overstorey canopy cover declined while understorey increased in both coniferous and broadleaved protected forests in Central Europe since 2019; and (2) overstorey–understorey canopy cover changes are significantly correlated in coniferous but not in broadleaved forests. The magnitude of change, however, is lower with the 5 m threshold.

Second, we tested a height-adaptive threshold based on RH100 (100th percentile relative height). For GEDI footprints with $RH100 < 20$ m we used 5 m, and for $RH100 \geq 20$ m we used 10 m, following Korpela et al. (2023). Results are broadly similar to those with the 10 m threshold (Section S2 and S7), though correlations between overstorey and understorey canopy cover change decrease slightly in coniferous forests and increase in broadleaved forests. This method is empirical and adapts only to forest height (RH100), not the vertical structure within footprints. Incorporating canopy cover profiles from GEDI Level 1B waveforms could better capture vertical stratification, as footprints of similar height often differ substantially in canopy distribution (Yun et al., 2023). However, this approach was not pursued here due to high computational demands at large spatial scales.

Previous studies confirm that understorey detectability in GEDI data depends on forest type, structure, and quality filters. Li et al. (2024), for instance, validated GEDI canopy cover against airborne lidar scanning (ALS) and found stronger agreement in coniferous than broadleaved forests and for stands > 10 m tall. Yun et al. (2023) showed that masking understorey improves canopy cover accuracy. Accuracy is further influenced by GEDI footprint geolocation (≈ 10 m in version 2; Tang et al., 2023), which strongly affect geolocation uncertainty in mountainous regions. For example, Mandl et al. (2023) applied a 5 m threshold in the European Alps and found much lower agreement between GEDI and ALS for understorey than for overstorey canopy cover.

In general, interception of laser pulses by dense overstorey canopies limits both airborne and spaceborne lidar in estimating understorey canopy cover. Terrestrial laser scanning (TLS), in contrast, records detailed structure from multiple ground-based perspectives (Calders et al., 2020), offering a valuable reference for GEDI-based understorey estimates. Waveform lidar metrics have also been linked to TLS-derived understorey properties such as canopy cover (Crespo-Peremarch et al., 2018). Future studies should explore these connections further.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we use GEDI derived canopy cover of overstorey and understorey to quantify the forest structure dynamics in Central Europe from 2019 to the beginning of 2023.

First, we found in many forests a decline of overstorey canopy cover, which we quantified for different protected forest areas and countries. For example, the overstorey canopy decreases by approximately 1.9 % per year in coniferous forests and by approximately 1.2 % per year in broadleaved forests in protected forests in Germany. The spatial patterns of these declines are consistent with other remote sensing products.

Second, we found that most of protected areas show an increase in understorey canopy cover for both forest types. On the one hand, the increase in understorey canopy cover can be caused by exposing existing understorey vegetation to lidar beams and on the other hand by an enhanced growth of existing understorey vegetation and by succession of new plants. Our results suggest that the increased exposure of the understorey vegetation to the lidar beams is not the dominant cause of increasing understorey canopy cover but that this is caused by forest regeneration, especially in disturbed coniferous forests that is undergoing since 2019.

Third, we found that GEDI canopy cover change in overstorey is negatively correlated ($r = -0.78$, $p < 0.01$) with canopy cover change of understorey in coniferous forests. While this relationship is indicative for a potentially high degree of post-disturbance forest regrowth, the increase in understorey canopy cover is much slower than the decrease in overstorey canopy cover. A similar relationship does not exist in broadleaved forests.

In summary, we demonstrated that, despite the limited spatial and temporal coverage of GEDI, GEDI can provide detailed information on changes in forest vertical structure and can hence complement state of the art datasets on forest cover loss. Hence GEDI demonstrates potential to further investigate the impacts of those changes in vertical forests cover on ecosystem functioning and their impacts on the climate system through changes in regional biogeochemical cycles.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Xiao Liu: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Vítězslav Moudrý:** Writing – review & editing. **Bernhard Schuldt:** Writing – review & editing. **Matthias Forkel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.foreco.2025.123155](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2025.123155).

Data availability

The data used in this study are publicly available.

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